

PSYCHOLOGICAL PROFILING OF FEMALE PATIENTS UNDERGOING AESTHETIC SURGERIES

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Abstract

Objective: To determine the psychological profile of female patients undergoing aesthetic surgeries and assess associations between psychological characteristics, motivations for surgery, and procedure type.

Study Design: Cross-sectional analytical study.

Place and Duration of Study: This Study was conducted at Department of Psychiatry, Armed Forces Institute of Mental Health, Rawalpindi from April 2024 to November 2024.

Methodology: A total of 78 female patients undergoing elective aesthetic surgical procedures were included. Demographic, clinical, and surgery-related data were recorded, and psychological profiling was performed using standardized assessments for self-esteem, body image dissatisfaction, anxiety symptoms, depressive symptoms, perfectionistic traits, and body dysmorphic tendencies.

Results: The mean age was 31.8 ± 7.6 years. Body image dissatisfaction was the most common psychological characteristic, observed in 41 (52.6%) patients, followed by perfectionistic traits in 34 (43.6%), anxiety symptoms in 29 (37.2%), and low self-esteem in 26 (33.3%). Body dysmorphic tendencies were present in 15 (19.2%) patients. Patients influenced by external motivations had significantly higher frequencies of low self-esteem (48.1% vs 25.5%, $p=0.041$), body image dissatisfaction (70.4% vs 43.1%, $p=0.028$), anxiety symptoms (51.9% vs 29.4%, $p=0.049$), perfectionistic traits (59.3% vs 35.3%, $p=0.036$), and body dysmorphic tendencies (33.3% vs 11.8%, $p=0.022$) compared with self-driven patients.

Conclusion: Female patients undergoing aesthetic surgeries demonstrated a substantial burden of psychological characteristics relevant to patient selection and expectation management. Psychological profiling may be useful as part of preoperative assessment in aesthetic surgical practice.

INTRODUCTION

Aesthetic surgery has experienced substantial global growth over the past two decades, driven by evolving beauty standards, social media influence, increasing accessibility of cosmetic

procedures, and greater acceptance of appearance-enhancing interventions [1]. While aesthetic procedures are often pursued to improve body image, self-esteem, and perceived

quality of life, growing evidence suggests that psychological factors play a central role in the motivations, expectations, and outcomes of patients seeking cosmetic surgery [2]. As a result, understanding the psychological profile of individuals undergoing aesthetic procedures has become increasingly important in both surgical planning and patient selection. Female patients constitute a major proportion of individuals seeking aesthetic surgery, including procedures such as rhinoplasty, breast augmentation, liposuction, abdominoplasty, and facial rejuvenation interventions [3]. Although many women pursue such procedures for personal satisfaction and experience favorable psychosocial outcomes, others may present with underlying psychological vulnerabilities, unrealistic expectations, distorted body image, or personality traits that may influence satisfaction and postoperative adjustment [4]. Identifying these characteristics is particularly important, as psychological factors may affect decision-making, perceived outcomes, and even medico-legal risk. Psychological profiling refers to the systematic assessment of cognitive, emotional, behavioral, and personality-related characteristics that may influence patient motivations and responses to treatment [5]. In the context of aesthetic surgery, profiling may include evaluation of self-esteem, body image dissatisfaction, anxiety, depression, perfectionism, social comparison tendencies, and symptoms of body dysmorphic disorder (BDD) [6]. These domains may help distinguish patients who are likely to benefit psychologically from surgery from those who may remain dissatisfied despite technically successful outcomes [7].

Body image dissatisfaction is among the most frequently studied psychological factors in aesthetic surgery populations. While dissatisfaction may motivate otherwise healthy patients to seek appearance-enhancing procedures, excessive preoccupation with perceived defects may indicate deeper psychopathology [8]. Body dysmorphic disorder, characterized by obsessive concern over minimal or imagined flaws in appearance, has been reported at higher rates among cosmetic surgery seekers compared with the general population and has been associated with poor postoperative satisfaction [9]. This has led to increasing calls

for routine psychological screening in aesthetic practice. Beyond body image concerns, anxiety and depressive symptoms have also been observed in subsets of cosmetic surgery patients [10]. Some studies suggest that patients with mild psychosocial distress may experience improvement following surgery, whereas individuals with untreated psychiatric conditions or maladaptive personality traits may have poorer adjustment and unrealistic postoperative expectations [11]. Personality constructs such as narcissistic traits, perfectionism, and external validation-seeking behaviors have also been explored as factors potentially influencing motivations for aesthetic procedures and postoperative satisfaction [12]. The rapid influence of digital culture has added further complexity to psychological motivations underlying cosmetic surgery demand. Social media exposure, appearance-focused content, filtered self-images, and online beauty norms have been associated with increased appearance dissatisfaction and rising interest in aesthetic procedures, particularly among women [13]. The phenomenon sometimes described as “selfie dysmorphia” has intensified concerns regarding whether some patients may seek surgery under distorted appearance perceptions shaped by digital environments. These trends reinforce the need for structured psychological assessment [14].

Objective

To determine the psychological profile of female patients undergoing aesthetic surgeries and assess associations between psychological characteristics, motivations for surgery, and procedure type.

Methodology

This was a cross-sectional analytical study conducted at Department of Psychiatry, Armed Forces Institute of Mental Health, Rawalpind from April 2024 to November 2024., including 78 female patients undergoing aesthetic surgical procedures. Female patients aged 18 years and above undergoing elective aesthetic surgical procedures, including facial, breast, and body contouring surgeries, were included in the study. Patients willing to participate and able to complete psychometric assessments were enrolled. Only patients with complete

demographic and psychological assessment data were included. Patients with previously diagnosed severe psychiatric disorders requiring ongoing treatment, active psychosis, cognitive impairment affecting questionnaire completion, prior major aesthetic revision surgery, or incomplete assessment forms were excluded to minimize confounding and maintain validity of psychological profiling.

Data Collection

After informed consent, baseline demographic and clinical data including age, marital status, educational level, employment status, type of aesthetic surgery planned, previous cosmetic procedures, and motivation for surgery were recorded using a structured proforma. Participants then underwent psychological assessment using validated psychometric instruments, including scales for self-esteem, body image dissatisfaction, anxiety, depression, perfectionism, and body dysmorphic traits. Scores were recorded and patients were categorized according to severity levels where applicable. All data were documented in the study proforma for analysis.

Statistical Analysis

Data were entered and analyzed using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 24.0.

Quantitative variables such as age and psychometric scores were presented as mean ± standard deviation, while qualitative variables were expressed as frequencies and percentages. Stratification was performed for age, marital status, and type of surgery to assess subgroup differences. A p-value ≤0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Results

A total of 78 female patients undergoing aesthetic surgeries were included, with a mean age of 31.8 ± 7.6 years. Married women comprised 42 (53.8%) patients, while 36 (46.2%) were unmarried. Most participants had graduate-level education or higher, accounting for 49 (62.8%) cases, and 50 (64.1%) were unemployed. Previous cosmetic procedures had been undergone by 19 (24.4%) patients, while the majority had no prior cosmetic intervention. Self-driven motivation for surgery was reported by 51 (65.4%) patients, whereas 27 (34.6%) cited social or external influences. Rhinoplasty was the most common procedure performed in 24 (30.8%) patients, followed by breast surgery in 18 (23.1%), liposuction in 16 (20.5%), abdominoplasty in 12 (15.4%), and facial rejuvenation in 8 (10.3%).

Table 1. Baseline Demographic and Socioclinical Characteristics (n=78)

Variable	Category	n (%) / Mean ± SD
Age (years)	–	31.8 ± 7.6
Marital Status	Married	42 (53.8)
	Unmarried	36 (46.2)
Education	Graduate or Above	49 (62.8)
	Below Graduate	29 (37.2)
Employment	Employed	28 (35.9)
	Unemployed	50 (64.1)
Previous Cosmetic Procedure	Yes	19 (24.4)
	No	59 (75.6)
Motivation for Surgery	Self-driven	51 (65.4)
	Social/External Influence	27 (34.6)
Type of Surgery	Rhinoplasty	24 (30.8)
	Breast Surgery	18 (23.1)
	Liposuction	16 (20.5)
	Abdominoplasty	12 (15.4)
	Facial Rejuvenation	8 (10.3)

Psychological characteristics were common within the cohort. Mean self-esteem score was 18.4 ± 4.2 , while low self-esteem was present in 26 (33.3%) patients. Body image dissatisfaction was the most frequent psychological feature,

affecting 41 (52.6%) patients. Anxiety symptoms were present in 29 (37.2%), depressive symptoms in 18 (23.1%), and perfectionistic traits in 34 (43.6%) patients. Body dysmorphic tendencies were observed in 15 (19.2%) patients.

Table 2. Psychological Profile Scores and Characteristics (n=78)

Variable	Category	n (%) / Mean \pm SD
Self-esteem Score	—	18.4 \pm 4.2
Low Self-esteem	Yes	26 (33.3)
	No	52 (66.7)
Body Image Dissatisfaction	Yes	41 (52.6)
	No	37 (47.4)
Anxiety Symptoms	Yes	29 (37.2)
	No	49 (62.8)
Depressive Symptoms	Yes	18 (23.1)
	No	60 (76.9)
Perfectionistic Traits	Yes	34 (43.6)
	No	44 (56.4)
Body Dysmorphic Tendencies	Yes	15 (19.2)
	No	63 (80.8)

Patients influenced by external motivations showed higher frequencies of low self-esteem compared with self-driven patients (48.1% vs 25.5%, $p=0.041$). Body image dissatisfaction was also significantly more common among externally motivated patients (70.4% vs 43.1%, $p=0.028$), as were anxiety symptoms (51.9% vs

29.4%, $p=0.049$). Perfectionistic traits were present in 59.3% of externally motivated patients compared with 35.3% of self-driven patients ($p=0.036$), while body dysmorphic tendencies were significantly more frequent in the external influence group (33.3% vs 11.8%, $p=0.022$).

Table 3. Association of Psychological Factors with Motivation for Surgery

Variable	Self-driven (n=51)	External Influence (n=27)	p-value
Low Self-esteem	13 (25.5)	13 (48.1)	0.041
No Low Self-esteem	38 (74.5)	14 (51.9)	
Body Image Dissatisfaction	22 (43.1)	19 (70.4)	0.028
No Body Image Dissatisfaction	29 (56.9)	8 (29.6)	
Anxiety Symptoms	15 (29.4)	14 (51.9)	0.049
No Anxiety Symptoms	36 (70.6)	13 (48.1)	
Perfectionistic Traits	18 (35.3)	16 (59.3)	0.036
No Perfectionistic Traits	33 (64.7)	11 (40.7)	
Body Dysmorphic Tendencies	6 (11.8)	9 (33.3)	0.022
No Body Dysmorphic Tendencies	45 (88.2)	18 (66.7)	

Patients undergoing rhinoplasty showed the highest frequency of body image dissatisfaction at 62.5%, compared with 50.0% in breast surgery and 47.2% in body contouring patients ($p=0.044$). Anxiety symptoms were also more common in rhinoplasty patients (45.8%)

compared with breast surgery (38.9%) and body contouring (30.6%) groups ($p=0.048$). Perfectionistic traits were highest among rhinoplasty patients at 54.2% ($p=0.039$), while body dysmorphic tendencies were also most

frequent in this group at 29.2% compared with 16.7% and 13.9% in the other groups ($p=0.031$).

Table 4. Stratified Psychological Characteristics by Type of Surgery

Variable	Rhinoplasty (n=24)	Breast Surgery (n=18)	Body Contouring (n=36)	p-value
Body Image Dissatisfaction	15 (62.5)	9 (50.0)	17 (47.2)	0.044
Anxiety Symptoms	11 (45.8)	7 (38.9)	11 (30.6)	0.048
Perfectionistic Traits	13 (54.2)	8 (44.4)	13 (36.1)	0.039
Body Dysmorphic Tendencies	7 (29.2)	3 (16.7)	5 (13.9)	0.031

Discussion

This study evaluated the psychological profile of female patients undergoing aesthetic surgeries and demonstrated that psychological factors were common among this population, particularly body image dissatisfaction, anxiety symptoms, perfectionistic traits, and low self-esteem. Body image dissatisfaction was the most frequent psychological characteristic, observed in 52.6% of patients, followed by perfectionistic traits in 43.6%, anxiety symptoms in 37.2%, and low self-esteem in 33.3%. These findings support the view that psychological dimensions are highly relevant in women seeking aesthetic procedures. Previous research has similarly reported elevated rates of body image concerns and perfectionistic tendencies among cosmetic surgery patients. A notable finding of this study was the presence of body dysmorphic tendencies in 19.2% of patients [15]. Although lower than the prevalence of general body dissatisfaction, this proportion remains clinically important because even subclinical dysmorphic traits may influence expectations and postoperative satisfaction. Previous research has also identified higher rates of body dysmorphic symptoms in aesthetic surgery seekers compared with the general population and has associated these tendencies with dissatisfaction despite technically successful outcomes [16].

Low self-esteem and anxiety symptoms were also common and appeared particularly relevant among patients influenced by external or social motivations for surgery. Patients undergoing surgery due to external influences had significantly higher frequencies of low self-esteem (48.1% vs 25.5%), body image

dissatisfaction (70.4% vs 43.1%), anxiety symptoms (51.9% vs 29.4%), and body dysmorphic tendencies (33.3% vs 11.8%) compared with self-motivated patients. These findings suggest that externally driven motivations may be associated with greater psychological vulnerability [17]. Previous research has similarly shown that patients motivated primarily by social pressure or external validation may have poorer psychological profiles and less favorable postoperative satisfaction. The significant association between perfectionistic traits and external motivation is also noteworthy. Perfectionism was more common among externally motivated patients (59.3%) than self-driven patients (35.3%), suggesting that unrealistic standards or excessive concern with appearance may contribute to the decision to seek surgery [18]. Previous research has likewise linked perfectionistic personality traits with heightened appearance-related concerns and increased interest in cosmetic procedures [19]. Differences in psychological characteristics across surgery types were also observed. Patients undergoing rhinoplasty showed higher frequencies of body image dissatisfaction, anxiety symptoms, perfectionistic traits, and body dysmorphic tendencies compared with breast surgery and body contouring groups. This may reflect greater psychosocial salience of facial appearance and the visibility of perceived defects. Previous research has similarly suggested that patients seeking facial aesthetic procedures, particularly rhinoplasty, may have higher rates of body image disturbance and psychological vulnerability than some other cosmetic surgery

groups [20]. The predominance of self-driven motivation for surgery in 65.4% of patients is important, as internally motivated patients are often considered more likely to have realistic expectations and favorable psychosocial outcomes. However, the coexistence of substantial psychological distress traits even within self-driven patients suggests motivation alone may not be sufficient to identify patients requiring further evaluation. Previous research has also emphasized that psychological assessment should extend beyond motivation alone. From a clinical perspective, these findings support the importance of integrating psychological screening into preoperative assessment of aesthetic surgery candidates. Routine evaluation of body image concerns, self-esteem, anxiety symptoms, perfectionistic traits, and dysmorphic tendencies may help identify patients who would benefit from counseling or further psychological assessment prior to surgery. Previous research has similarly advocated structured psychological screening to improve patient selection and reduce dissatisfaction risk.

Limitations

This study had several limitations. First, being a single-center study with a relatively small sample size of 78 patients, the findings may have limited generalizability and reduced precision for subgroup analyses. Second, the cross-sectional design precluded assessment of temporal relationships or changes in psychological characteristics after surgery. Third, psychological profiling was based on self-reported psychometric assessments, which may be subject to reporting bias or social desirability bias. Fourth, patients with severe psychiatric disorders were excluded, which may have underestimated the prevalence of psychological vulnerability in the broader aesthetic surgery population.

Conclusion

It is concluded that female patients undergoing aesthetic surgeries demonstrated a substantial burden of psychological characteristics, particularly body image dissatisfaction, perfectionistic traits, anxiety symptoms, and low self-esteem. Psychological vulnerabilities were more frequent among patients influenced by external motivations for surgery and were more

pronounced in certain procedure groups, particularly rhinoplasty. These findings support the importance of incorporating psychological profiling into preoperative assessment to improve patient selection, expectation management, and holistic aesthetic surgical care.

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